

Exam Stress and Emotional Eating among Lebanese University Students: A Correlational Study

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Abstract

Background: Integrating university students into an academic environment can be intense, with significant intellectual and emotional challenges. Stress, particularly during exam periods, plays a crucial role in students' eating habits, often influencing their food choice through mechanisms such as emotional eating.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted among 700 students aged 18 to 25 years in Lebanon, using online questionnaires to assess perceived stress using the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) and emotional eating behaviors with the Dutch Eating Behavior Questionnaire (DEBQ). Data were analyzed to identify correlations between stress and emotional eating.

Results: A significant positive correlation was observed between levels of perceived stress and increased emotional eating, with marked differences depending on participants' gender and field of study. This trend highlights the concerning impact of academic stress on students' food choices, including an increased prevalence of emotional eating among women and those studying in demanding disciplines like health sciences and engineering.

Conclusion: This research contributes to the understanding of the complex links between academic stress and emotional eating behaviors among university students in Lebanon. To improve the mental and physical health of students, it is essential to implement tailored educational and support initiatives aimed at reducing stress and promoting balanced dietary choices in learning environments.

More Information

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Exam stress, emotional eating, university students, stress management, Lebanon.

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Introduction

Integration into a university academic career is often compared to immersion in a dynamic arena marked by intellectual challenges, personal growth and the quest for a balanced and healthy lifestyle. However, this phase of transformation is frequently accompanied by an omnipresent and silent phenomenon: stress. During exam periods, in particular, stress can seep into various aspects of a student's life, including influencing their eating behaviors.

Emotional eating was selected as one of the primary foci because it is a partially unconscious type of coping indicating real, reactions to stress, which is especially important in the context of intensive stress like the examination period in university. Emotional hunger, on the other hand, arises due to feelings and can result in dependency on food to deal with the feeling. It is an important variable to study because this kind of behavior is evident among learners when they

transition to new academic and social expectations, therefore making it easy to investigate in relation to stress in a university setting. This behavior is often used as a means of stress management, providing comfort and distraction in intense emotional situations [1]. It can be triggered by positive emotions such as celebrations or negative emotions such as stress and anxiety, thus constituting a stress coping mechanism that is often poorly adapted in the long term. Few investigations in Lebanon investigate the phenomenon of emotional eating under such specific socio-cultural stressors, offering this study a chance to bring light to local trends and contributory factors.

Stress was selected over other common psychological disorders, such as depression and anxiety, because stress is a universally familiar phenomenon for most learners during examinations experience in both psychological and physiological forms due pressures perceived as threatening or difficult to manage [2].

Stress that comes as a result of examinations affects eating directly since it reduces appetite, distorts food choices and increases the desire for calorie dense comfort foods is a complex reaction that encompasses physiological and psychological disturbances.

The importance of this study is anchored on the need to look at stress and emotional eating among Lebanese university students given the enhanced academic pressure coupled with tough socio-economic conditions that have been experienced within the region. In addition to stress which is inherent to students around the world, the Lebanese students experience extra strain as a result of the political and economic situation in the country. Things like increased costs, fewer job opportunities, and constant upheaval in development can exacerbate that stress, thus the eating. In Lebanon, there is scarce research that focuses on how such specific stressors affect the students' mental health and behavior. Most of the literature reviewed is drawn from western social and cultural settings, which might not fully characterize the challenges faced by Lebanese students in respect of socio-cultural, economic or political differences. Thus, the present research is essential in filling the current gap in the literature by offering local data and concepts for culturally appropriate interventions. Such context-sensitive study is needed for developing support programs and policies which would not only encompass academic pressure, but also other socio-economic pressures influencing student's experience in Lebanon as well.

This study's focus on stress might be describes as students' generic reaction to study without involving deeper pathologies, which enables to be concentrate on how the stress connected with academic performance influences dietary behavior in a specific and rather well-prognostic context. Moreover, it is easier to measure stress effectively in the short-term conditions such as exams guaranteeing the thorough analysis of its immediate impact on the eating behavior. During university exam periods, academic stress can lead to unbalanced eating behaviors, including emotional eating. Studies show that women tend to rely more on food to manage stress compared to men, which may contribute to eating disorders like bulimia [2,3]. This emotional overconsumption can be exacerbated by socio-demographic and psychological factors, negatively affecting the overall health of individuals.

This research focuses on the relationship between stress levels during exam periods and the eating habits of university students in Lebanon, with a focus on emotional eating (EE). Emotional eating is a behavior where individuals consume food in response to emotions, whether positive or negative. Psychologically, stress triggers bodily responses as

individuals seek ways to cope with the tension, while physiologically, stress activates the nervous system, leading to changes in appetite that influence eating behaviors.

Methodology

Ethical Approval

This study was approved by the ethics committee of the Lebanese German University, ensuring that all procedures met the ethical standards for research involving humans. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement in the study, guaranteeing that they were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and their rights as participants.

Study Design

A cross-sectional study was conducted among 700 students aged 18 to 25, enrolled in different universities in Lebanon during the fall semester of 2023. The participant selection process is illustrated in the flow chart below (Figure 1). Inclusion criteria included being a currently enrolled university student within the specified age range and residing in Lebanon. Exclusion criteria involved students outside this age range, those not enrolled in a Lebanese university, and any participant with a history of diagnosed eating disorders or severe mental health conditions, as these could impact emotional eating behaviors independently of academic stress.

Figure 1: Participants Flow Chart

The sampling was conducted using stratified randomization to ensure representativeness across different disciplines and academic levels. Universities were first grouped by academic discipline categories (such as health sciences, engineering, humanities, etc.) and then by academic year (first-year through fifth-year students). Within each stratum, students were randomly selected using a computer-generated randomization list to minimize selection bias and ensure a diverse and balanced sample.

The questionnaire was distributed online via platforms such as WhatsApp, which facilitated wide dissemination and contributed to a high response rate. Participants were asked to complete the questionnaire

anonymously to encourage honest responses and reduce social bias.

Questionnaire

The questionnaire was divided into several parts: Demographic and Socioeconomic Questions: This section collected essential information about participants, including age, gender, field of study, academic year, employment status, and living conditions. These variables were used to analyze potential sociodemographic influences on stress and emotional eating behaviors.

Perceived Stress: Stress levels were assessed using the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS), specifically the Arabic version validated by [10]. The PSS is a 10-item scale that measures the general perception of stress, asking participants to rate the frequency of their feelings and thoughts related to stress over the past month. Each item is rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 0 (never) to 4 (very often), with a total possible score ranging from 0 to 40. Higher scores on the PSS indicate greater perceived stress. Cutoff values are often categorized as follows: low stress (0–13), moderate stress (14–26), and high stress (27–40).

Emotional Eating Behaviors: Emotional eating was measured using the Dutch Eating Behavior Questionnaire (DEBQ), which has been validated for the Lebanese population [4]. The DEBQ consists of 13 items related to emotional eating, each assessing the tendency to eat in response to emotions. Items are rated on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (never) to 5 (very often). A higher total score on the DEBQ’s emotional eating subscale indicates a greater tendency toward emotional eating behaviors. Scores are interpreted based on relative tendencies rather than fixed cutoff values, with higher scores reflecting a stronger pattern of emotional eating.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS software v.26. Pearson correlation test was used to identify the relationship between perceived stress and emotional eating behaviors. Partial correlation was conducted afterwards to assess the same relationship, after adjustment over all sociodemographic and other variables. The results were considered statistically significant at a level of $p < 0.05$.

Results

Most participants were women (59%) and had a healthy BMI (59%). First year (44.6%) and second year (26.6%) students were the most represented. 28.6% of participants were employed full time and financially dependent. The majority of students were enrolled in the health and paramedical sciences fields (32.7%). Most participants lived with their parents (86.7%) and preferred to study alone (75.3%).

Table 1. Sociodemographic and Other Characteristics of the Participants (n = 700)

Gender	
Male	286 (40.9%)
Female	414 (59.1%)
Marital status	
Single	697 (99.6%)
Married	3 (0.4%)
Employment	
Unemployed	184 (26.3%)
Full time and financially dependent	200 (28.6%)
Full time and financially independent	176 (25.1%)
Part time and financially dependent	83 (11.9%)
Part time and financially independent	57 (8.1%)
Current major of study	
Health and paramedical sciences	229 (32.7%)
Business	137 (19.6%)
Humanities	52 (7.4%)
Psychology and politics	88 (12.6%)
Sciences	123 (17.6%)
Engineering	71 (10.1%)
Current year of study	
First	186 (26.6%)
Second	312 (44.6%)
Third	124 (17.7%)
Fourth	53 (7.6%)
Fifth	25 (3.6%)
Living situation	
With parents	607 (86.7%)
Alone	93 (13.3%)
Age (years)	21.23 ± 2.16
Stress	23.22 ± 3.77
Emotional eating	43.97 ± 8.10

Analysis of Stress Levels

Among the investigated students, 81% of the participants had a moderate level of stress according to the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) score. Using subjects self-completed stress scales, statistical analysis indicated that female participants reported slightly elevated stress compared to male participants with the difference found to be statistically significant by the $t = 2.34$ independent t - test that compared female and male mean stress scores. Furthermore, male students indicated that they experienced higher levels of stress compared to female students, and students taking rigorous courses in the health sciences and engineering disciplines appeared to be more stressed than students at other disciplines. These conclusions were drawn through One-Way ANOVA to compare across subjects,

implied by the authors that this stress may be due to increased academic pressure inherent in such courses.

Emotional Eating

A high percentage of students 82% was found to have high levels of emotional eating during periods of stress, they recorded high mean emotional eating score of 43.97 ± 8.10 . The results also suggested that women scored higher than men in the emotional eating, which may have been further affirmed by the independent t-test comparing for emotional eating scores. Moreover, health and allied health sciences (32.7%), engineering (10.1%), sciences (17.6%), arts and humanities (19.2%) students also showed significantly high emotional eating using one-way ANOVA across different majors. The above statistics such as the stress score having a mean value of 23.22 ± 3.77 also termed the stress the relationship between stress and emotional eating behavior among students. The assessment indicates that the amount of students with high scores signaling a propensity to use food to combat stress is quite high. Differences between the gender variables were recorded, where in general, women were found to emotional eat more than men, most probably when tested using another independent t-test on the scores of emotional eating. Moreover, the students from the hard academic programs including health and paramedical sciences, engineering, and science consumed high levels of emotional foods, according to the one-way ANOVA results regarding the specialties of students. The average stress score of 23.22 ± 3.77 is a supplement to this finding and emphasizes the correlation between stress and students' emotional eating behaviors.

Correlation between Stress and Emotional Eating

A significant positive correlation was identified between stress levels and emotional eating behaviors ($r = 0.092$; $p = 0.015$). When adjusting over other covariates (age, sex, marital status, employment, living situation, major of study and year of study), the results showed that higher stress positively and significantly correlated with higher emotional eating ($r = 0.097$; $p = 0.011$).

Discussion

This study aimed to examine the relationship between stress and emotional eating among university students during exam periods. The findings confirmed a positive and statistically significant correlation between higher stress levels and increased emotional eating ($r = 0.097$; $p = 0.011$). This suggests that stress experienced during exams can lead students to engage in emotional eating as a coping mechanism. These findings align with existing literature, where stress-related physiological responses, such as the release of cortisol, can increase appetite and cravings for calorie-dense, comfort foods [5,6]. This stress-induced increase in appetite reinforces the connection between heightened stress

and eating behaviors driven by emotions rather than physical hunger.

Emotional eating as a response to stress may be particularly relevant for students in the Lebanese context, where they face not only academic pressures but also unique socio-economic and political stressors. Such compounded stressors can exacerbate the tendency toward emotional eating, with students potentially using food as a form of distraction or comfort in the face of challenges both inside and outside the academic environment. This points to the importance of addressing stress management in a way that reflects the full range of stressors impacting Lebanese university students.

Gender differences in emotional eating behaviors were also observed, with prior studies suggesting that women are generally more likely than men to use food as a coping mechanism under stress [7]. The greater tendency among women toward emotional eating may be influenced by distinct emotional processing patterns, where women may be more likely to use food in response to sadness, anxiety, or anger. This suggests that gender-specific approaches may be beneficial in interventions targeting stress-related eating behaviors. The findings highlight a need for supportive programs and stress management resources within university settings, particularly for first-year students who are often adjusting to academic workloads and new social dynamics. Evidence suggests that structured, early preparation and social support can lower the inclination toward emotional eating compared to last-minute studying or studying alone [8,9] Furthermore, students' living situations may also play a role, with those living alone displaying higher levels of emotional eating than those living with family [2]. This may reflect reduced social support or increased loneliness, which can amplify stress and, consequently, emotional eating behaviors.

Thus, this study underscores the impact of stress on eating behaviors during exam periods, with increased stress leading to a heightened likelihood of emotional eating among students. By understanding this relationship, targeted interventions can be developed to address stress management, potentially improving students' mental and physical health outcomes in university settings and leading to the induction of effective stress management.

In that sense, effective stress management involves adopting healthy coping strategies such as practicing mindfulness, time management, and promoting balanced food choices even during times of academic pressure [2]. A holistic approach to mental and physical health would be essential to mitigate the negative effects of stress on eating behavior and improve overall student well-being.

Clinical Implications

The results of this study have significant clinical implications for researchers and health professionals. By identifying a positive correlation between academic stress and emotional eating in university students, this research highlights the need to develop targeted interventions to mitigate these behaviors. Mental health professionals, including psychologists and nutritionists, can use this information to develop stress management programs that include strategies to counter emotional eating. Furthermore, these findings can inform university policies aimed at promoting a more balanced academic environment by reducing stressors and providing accessible psychological support to students. Researchers can also use these data to further study the mechanisms underlying emotional eating, including exploring individual differences and effective interventions to reduce these behaviors in diverse cultural and academic contexts.

This study has limitations related to data collection difficulties as well as a restricted focus on certain factors influencing emotional eating. In addition, local economic conditions may have affected participants' responses, which reduces the scope of the conclusions and limits the generalizability of the results to other contexts or populations.

Some other possible bias could also have contributed to the results. There could be information bias relating to self-reporting of stress and emotional eating, as noted by participants, since participants are inclined to giving either a lower or higher report of the average stress level and the frequency of emotional eating compared to the actual figures. People might have overestimated or underestimated their stress levels, or the degree of emotional eating, which influences the validity of the outcomes.

Sample selection bias arises as another potential bias that could arise due to the population of the study being limited to university students in Lebanon. It may not be a true reflection of the population of students, other youth not in university or even youths in other cultures therefore the results may not hold well with other such demography.

Lastly, residual confounding bias may also be present, as there are likely additional unmeasured variables influencing both stress and emotional eating behaviors. Factors such as personal coping styles, pre-existing mental health conditions, and family dynamics, which were not accounted for in this study, could influence the observed relationship between stress and emotional eating. Future research should consider these variables to reduce potential confounding and improve the accuracy of findings.

Conclusion

This study highlights the significant impact of stress on the eating behaviors of university students in Lebanon,

a phenomenon also observed globally. It also provides valuable insight into the impact of academic stress on college students' eating behaviors. It highlights the importance of stress management strategies to improve students' quality of life and promote healthy eating behaviors. Understanding this relationship is crucial for developing effective interventions to reduce stress and promote mental health among college students.

Future research could focus on developing and evaluating intervention programs specifically targeting stress management and emotional eating among college students. These programs could include relaxation techniques, nutritional counseling, and regular physical activity, all of which have been shown to reduce stress and improve overall well-being. Academic institutions are recommended to invest in creating supportive environments and wellness programs to support students' academic success and overall well-being.

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